

Linear sweep voltammetric determination of chondroitin sulfate based on its interaction with pyronine B

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Abstract : A new linear sweep voltammetric method was proposed for the detection of chondroitin sulfate (CS) by using pyronine B (PB) as electrochemical probe. In the selected pH 1.5 Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution, PB has a sensitive linear sweep voltammetric reduction peak at -0.78 V (vs SCE). After the addition of CS into PB solution, the reduction peak current decreased apparently without the shift of reduction peak potential. The conditions for the interaction and electrochemical detection were optimized. Under the optimal conditions, the decrease of reduction peak current was proportional to the concentration of CS in the range of 2.0–50.0 mg/L with the linear regression equation as $\Delta I_p''(\text{nA}) = 23.90 + 83.43C$ (mg/L) ($n = 13$, $\gamma = 0.994$) and the detection limit as 0.84 mg/L (3σ). Three synthetic samples were determined with satisfactory results and the stoichiometry of CS with PB was calculated by the voltammetric data.

Keywords : Linear sweep voltammetry, chondroitin sulfate, pyronine B.

Chondroitin sulfate (CS) is a polysaccharide of glycosaminoglycan with alternating D-glucuronic acid and N-acetylated-D-galactosamine residues¹. CS was firstly isolated from cartilage in 1884 and it has many medical functions. For example, it is part of proteoglycans found on the surfaces of cell in the extracellular matrix, and plays important roles in cell-cell communications². It can also be found in the connective tissues in the form of proteoglycans³. Otherwise, CS has many clinical applications such as the administration of CS as a supplement or a drug for the treatment of osteoarthritis, the prevention of subsequent coronary events, treatment of psoriasis and ophthalmic diseases⁴. Therefore, it is important to establish a sensitive determination method for CS.

Some different kinds of analytical methods had been proposed for CS detection such as Elson-Morgan method^{5,6} and HPLC⁷. Recently some spectrophotometric methods were proposed for CS detection. Shi *et al.*⁸ used victoria pure blue BO for spectrophotometric detection of CS in the presence of emulsifier OP and phosphate buffer solution. Gao *et al.*⁹ established a rapid and precise spectrophotometric method for CS based on the reaction of CS with a mineral acid-containing phloroglucinol

solution. Gao *et al.*¹⁰ applied azure A for the quantitative assay of CS by measuring the absorbance of AA-CS complex at 625 nm. But there are no electrochemical methods for the determination of CS to our knowledge.

Electroanalysis had been successfully applied to the determination of different kinds of biomolecules such as DNA, protein and heparin. Since the electrochemical reaction takes place at the surface of the electrode and the solution, it has the characteristics of low detection limit and wider dynamic range with small amount of samples. For example, Tamiya *et al.*¹¹ studied the interaction of Hoechst 33258 with DNA in solution by linear sweep voltammetry and further established a DNA quantification method. Jiao *et al.*^{12,13} investigated the electrochemical behavior of toluidine blue and malachite green with dsDNA and detected the DNA content in the samples. Our group also proposed some electrochemical probes for the determination of biomolecules such as DNA^{14,15}, protein^{16,17} and heparin^{18,19}. Based on the changes of electrochemical responses, the proposed method is sensitive and successfully applied to the sample determinations.

In this paper, a simple linear sweep voltammetric

method was proposed for electrochemical determination of CS for the first time. In the selected buffer solution, CS was in negatively charged and easily interacted with the selected cationic dyes of pyronine B (PB, the molecular structure shown in Fig. 1) and resulted in the changes of the electrochemical response, which was further used for CS quantification.

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of pyronine B (PB).

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

The second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric measurements were performed on a JP-303 polarographic analyzer (Chengdu Apparatus Factory, China) with a traditional three-electrode system composed of a drop mercury working electrode (DME), a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire counter electrode. The values of the buffer pH were measured by a pHs-25 acidimeter (Shanghai Leici Instrument Factory, China). All the experiments were carried out at 25 ± 2 °C.

Chondroitin sulfate (CS, 99%, Shandong Linyi Tianli Biochemical Company) was used as received without further purification. A 1.0 g/L stock solution of CS was prepared by directly dissolving it into doubly distilled water and stored at 4 °C. A 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L pyronine B (PB, Shanghai Chemical Reagent Station, China) solution was used as stock solution. 0.2 mol/L Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer was used to adjust the pH values of test solution. All the other reagents were of analytical reagent grade and doubly distilled water was used throughout.

Procedures :

Into a 10 mL calibrated tube was added in sequence 2.0 mL of pH 1.5 B-R buffer, 0.6 mL of 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L PB and an appropriate amount of CS standard solution. The mixture was diluted to the scale and shaken homogeneously. After reaction at 25 °C for 20 min, the second order derivative voltammetric peak current (I_p'') was recorded in the potential range of $-0.45 \sim -1.05$ V (vs SCE). Under the same conditions, the solution without

the addition of CS was used as the blank solution and the voltammetric peak current (I_{p_0}'') was obtained. The decrease of peak current, which was presented by the equation ($\Delta I_p'' = I_{p_0}'' - I_p''$), was used to show the changes of electrochemical responses of the reaction system.

Results and discussion

Second order derivative linear sweep voltammogram :

Fig. 2 showed the typical second order derivative linear sweep voltammograms of PB and its mixture with CS. Curve 1 was the voltammogram of the B-R buffer solution and no voltammetric peak appeared. Curve 2 was the voltammogram of the PB in pH 1.5 B-R buffer solution, it had a well-defined voltammetric reductive peak at -0.78 V (vs SCE), which was due to the electrode reduction of xanthene group of PB. Curve 3 was the voltammogram of PB after the addition of CS, the peak current decreased greatly without the movement of peak potential. The result indicated that an interaction had taken place between CS and PB. Since CS is in negatively charged in the selected acidic buffer solution and PB is in positively charged, so the electrostatic attraction of CS with PB was happened in the mixed solution, which

Fig. 2. Second order derivative linear sweep polarographic curves of PB-CS reaction system : (1) 0.2 mol/L pH 1.5 B-R; (2) (1) + 6.0×10^{-5} mol/L PB; (3) (2) + 20.0 mg/L CS.

resulted in the decrease of the free concentration of PB in the solution and the decrease of reduction peak current. Based on this phenomenon, the decrease of the reductive peak current can be further used to establish a sensitive analytical method for micro-amount of CS.

Optimal of the reaction conditions :

The reaction conditions such as the acidity of buffer solution, the PB concentration, reaction time and the instrumental conditions *et al.* were carefully investigated.

The acidity and amount of buffer solution had great influences on the reaction system. The optimal pH for the binding reaction was selected in the pH range of 1.3 ~ 4.5 and the amount of B-R in the range of 0.5 ~ 5.0 mL. As shown in Fig. 3, the difference of peak current reached its maximum at pH 1.5, at this pH value CS was dissociated and hold negatively charge, it can easily interact with positively charged PB. The amount of pH 1.5 B-R solution was selected and 2.0 mL of B-R buffer was used for further investigation.

The effect of PB concentration on the peak current was tested by fixing the CS concentration at 30.0 mg/L and the results showed that when the concentration of PB was at 6.0×10^{-5} mol/L, the difference of peak currents reached its maximum. So a 6.0×10^{-5} mol/L PB concentration was chosen for further experiments. The binding reaction reached its equilibrium for about 20 min and remained constant for about 2 h. Therefore, 20 min of the incubation time was selected. The reaction temperature had little influence on the difference of the peak current in the temperature range from 10 to 50 °C and 25 °C was used thoroughly.

The instrumental conditions such as the scan rate and the drop mercury standing time for the assay were studied. The difference of peak current increased with the increase of scan rate from 300 to 750 mV/s and the drop mercury standing time from 5 to 12 s. The value of $\Delta I_p''$ reached maximum at 750 mV/s and decreased gradually. When the dropping mercury time was more than 11 s, the

Fig. 3. The influence of pH on the binding reaction : 30.0 mg/L CS + 2.0×10^{-4} mol/L PB in different pH B-R buffer.

mercury drop would fall down naturally. So the scan rate and the standing time were selected as 750 mV/s and 11 s, respectively.

Influences of coexisting substances :

Under the optimal conditions the influences of coexisting substances such as metal ions, amino acids, surfactants, DNA and proteins were examined for interferences on the determination of 30.0 mg/L CS. The results were shown in Table 1. It can be seen that most of them didn't interfere with the determination at the given concentration. Therefore the method can be directly applied to the practical sample determination.

Working curve :

Under the selected conditions and based on the decrease of the second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric peak current, an electrochemical quantitative method was developed for the determination of CS. A linear relationship between the decrease of peak currents ($\Delta I_p''$)

Table 1. Effect of foreign substances on the determination of 30.0 mg/L CS

Coexisting substance	Concentration (mol/L)	Relative error (%)	Coexisting substance	Concentration (mg/L)	Relative error (%)
Cu ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	-1.28	L-Tyrosine	1.0	-1.63
Ca ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	2.56	L-Leucine	1.0	-1.43
Co ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	2.90	L-Valine	1.0	-1.28
Sn ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	0.51	L-Arginine	1.0	1.08
Zn ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	-3.95	L-Glutamine	1.0	-3.25
Mg ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}	-3.99	L-Cystine	1.0	4.17
BHb ^a	1.0 mg/L	2.71	L-Cysteine	1.0	8.17
HSA ^a	1.0 mg/L	-6.16	Glycine	1.0	0.74
CTAB ^a	1.0 mg/L	-2.71	Glucose	1.0	-0.89
DNA ^a	1.0 mg/L	6.35	Citric acid	1.0	-4.37

^a(Bovine hemoglobin, BHb), (Human serum albumin, HSA), (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB), (deoxyribonucleic acid, DNA).

and the concentration of CS was established in the range of 2.0 ~ 50.0 mg/L with the linear regression equation as $\Delta I_p''(\text{nA}) = 83.43C(\text{mg/L}) + 23.90$ ($n = 13$, $\gamma = 0.994$). The RSD of the 10 parallel determinations of 20.0 mg/L CS was 1.11%. The detection limit was calculated to be 0.84 mg/L with the equation $\text{LOD} = 3S_0/S$, where 3 is the factor at the 99% confidential level, S_0 the standard deviation of the blank measurements ($n = 9$) and S the slope of calibration curve.

Sample determinations :

Three synthetic samples contained CS, metal ions, amino acids *et al.* were analyzed by the proposed method and the results were shown in Table 2. It can be seen that CS in synthetic samples can be determined with satisfactory results and the recovery was in the range of 96.23 ~ 97.86%.

where ΔI is the difference of peak current in the absence and presence of CS to the solution; ΔI_{max} corresponds the maximum value of difference of peak current; C_{CS} , $[\text{CS} - m\text{PB}]$ and $[\text{CS}]$ correspond to the total, bound and free concentration of CS in the solution, respectively.

From the eq. (6) the relationship of $\log [\Delta I/(\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I)]$ versus $\log [\text{PB}]$ was calculated and plotted with a linear regression equation as $\log [\Delta I/(\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I)] = 3.9 \log [\text{PB}] + 17.4$ ($n = 6$, $\gamma = 0.991$). From the intercept and the slope the value of $m = 4$ and $\beta_s = 2.51 \times 10^7$ were obtained, which indicated that a stable 1 : 4 complex of CS-4 PB was formed in the selected conditions.

Conclusions :

A simple second order derivative linear sweep

Table 2. Determination results of CS in synthetic samples ($n = 5$)

Samples	Coexisting substances	Added (mg/L)	Founded (mg/L)	RSD (%)	Recovery (%)
1.	L-Tyrosine, citric acid, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+}	10.00	9.71	2.39	97.14
2.	L-Leucine, glycine, Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+}	20.00	19.25	0.58	96.23
3.	L-Arginine, glucose, Sn^{2+} , Cu^{2+}	30.00	29.36	1.23	97.86

*Concentration of coexisting substances : L-tyrosine, citric acid, L-leucine, glycine, L-arginine, glucose (1.0 mg/L); Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} (1.0×10^{-6} mol/L).

Stoichiometry of CS-PB complex :

The composition of the CS-PB complex and the equilibrium constant of the system was calculated by the following method²⁰. It was assumed that PB interacted with CS only formed a single complex of CS- m PB. The binding number (m) and the equilibrium constant (β_s) of the binding reaction could be calculated as following :

The equilibrium constant was deduced as follows :

$$\beta_s = \frac{[\text{CS} - m\text{PB}]}{[\text{CS}][\text{PB}]^m} \quad (1)$$

Because of :

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} = k C_{\text{CS}} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta I = k [\text{CS} - m\text{PB}] \quad (3)$$

$$[\text{CS}] + [\text{CS} - m\text{PB}] = C_{\text{CS}} \quad (4)$$

Therefore :

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I = k (C_{\text{CS}} - [\text{CS} - m\text{PB}]) = k [\text{CS}] \quad (5)$$

Introducing (1), (3) and (5) gives :

$$\log [\Delta I/(\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I)] = \log \beta_s + m \log [\text{PB}] \quad (6)$$

voltammetric method for the determination of chondroitin sulfate (CS) was established using electroactive dyes of pyronine B (PB) for the first time in this paper. The conditions for interaction and electrochemical detection were optimized. Under the optimal conditions the CS can be detected in the concentration range of 2.0 ~ 50.0 mg/L. The established method was successfully applied to CS synthetic samples determination with satisfactorily results.

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